

ON THE BITTER PRINCIPLE FROM *ANDROGRAPHIS PANICULATA*, NEES. PART I.

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The formula and other properties ascribed to andrographolide, $C_{20}H_{30}O_5$, by Gorter have been confirmed. The presence of a methylenedioxy group has been proved. Triacetylandrographolide of Gorter could not be prepared. Hydrolysis of andrographolide gave two isomeric acids, $C_{20}H_{32}O_6$, one of which is probably identical with the known andrographolic acid. Iodine chloride indicated one double bond, but the catalytic hydrogenation of the bitter principle gave a dihydro derivative different from an isomeric dihydroandrographolide obtained by the action of stannous chloride.

Andrographis paniculata, Nees ("Kalmegh" in Bengali), is extensively used in the treatment of various diseases, such as disorders of the bowels and liver, colic, undiagnosed fevers, and also as a cholagogue and anthelmintic.

Dymock (*Pharmacographia Indica*, Vol. III, p. 47) reports the presence of a non-alkaloidal bitter principle, while Abderhalden ("Biochem. Handlexikon, Vol. VII, p. 230) mentions the bitter principle, andrographolide $C_{16}H_{27}O_4$, as colourless, odourless plates, sparingly soluble in water, but more easily in chloroform and ethyl acetate. It does not give tests for a glucoside, but dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a yellow colour which changes to purple-red on warming (Boorsma, *Jahresber. Pharm.*, 1897, 32, 43). Bhaduri (*Almer. J. Pharm.*, 1914, 84, 389) described two bitter principles (of *A. paniculata*), obviously impure, one of which formed yellow crystals, m.p. 206° , and contained OH groups, while the other was amorphous, m.p. 185° , to which the improbable formula, $C_{19}H_{51}O_5$ or $C_{19}H_{52}O_5$ was given. Gorter (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1911, 20, 151; 1914, 33, 236) prepared andrographolide in a pure condition. He assigned to it the formula, $C_{20}H_{30}O_5$ (m.p. 218° with decomposition; $[\alpha]_D^{26} = -126^\circ$ in 2% acetic acid). He also prepared a triacetyl derivative, m.p. 129° , and an amorphous additive product with hydrogen bromide namely $C_{20}H_{33}O_5Br_3$, and andrographolic acid, m.p. 188° (needles) having $[\alpha]_D^{26} = +14.4^\circ$. Gorter's conclusions are that andrographolide contains three OH groups one of which appears to be tertiary, besides a lactone ring and more than one double bond.

We have reinvestigated this bitter principle. Andrographolide, isolated by us from the leaves of fully mature plants in varying yields (1.5–2.5 per cent.) and purified by repeated crystallisations from suitable solvents, melts

at 220° (decomp.). It is extremely bitter even at very great dilutions. From analytical and saponification data the molecular formula, $C_{20}H_{30}O_5$, is confirmed. It has $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -123.5^{\circ}$ in 2% glacial acetic acid solution. It does not give tests for a glucoside and is indifferent towards ferric chloride, ammoniacal silver salts, Fehling's solution, bromine water and cold permanganate solution. Oxidation, however, takes place with warm permanganate solution. It is insoluble in cold dilute mineral acids or alkali, but dissolves in concentrated hydrochloric acid with a pink, and in concentrated sulphuric acid with a yellow colour, and is thrown down unchanged on dilution with water. The sulphuric acid solution becomes deep brown and shows a bright green fluorescence on warming.

On prolonged contact with or on warming with alkali, specially in presence of alcohol, andrographolide dissolves to a light yellow solution and is precipitated as a gum on acidification. If, however, the alkaline solution be carefully acidified, a crystalline acid, $C_{20}H_{32}O_6$, m.p. 156° , is obtained. We shall refer to this acid as *isoandrographolic acid*. It gives insoluble barium, calcium and lead salts and is transformed into the original substance on warming with dilute hydrochloric acid. On being warmed with a slight excess of ammonia, followed by acidification in the cold, *isoandrographolic acid* is converted into another isomeric acid, m.p. 180° , which is presumably identical with Gorter's andrographolic acid, $C_{20}H_{32}O_6$.

Andrographolide is recovered practically unchanged after heating for 5-10 minutes with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate. This is in sharp contrast with Gorter's experience. Acetylation in presence of a trace of concentrated sulphuric acid, however, rapidly gives a deep brown solution with a strong green fluorescence, from which a fluorescent gum is precipitated on dilution with water. This is presumably due to loss of water and carbon dioxide, since a similar product is obtained by dry heating at $225-30^{\circ}$, when the formation of water and carbon dioxide could be easily demonstrated. This indicates the presence of at least one OH group. The lactone ring probably supplies the carbon dioxide. Attempts to obtain a chloro compound by treating andrographolide with phosphorus oxychloride on the water-bath results in the formation of a solid product, which melts at 120° after purification and contains both phosphorus and chlorine. This is, however, found to be free from methylenedioxy group, which is originally present in andrographolide (*vide infra*). Treatment with phenyl isocyanate gives a white amorphous solid, m.p. $90-95^{\circ}$, containing nitrogen. All these reactions prove the presence of at least one OH group in the molecule. Distillation of andrographolide with 33% sulphuric acid gives formaldehyde. This indicates the presence of a methylenedioxy group

All the oxygen atom in andrographolide are thus accounted for. Two form the lactone ring, two are present in the methylenedioxy group, while the fifth is present as an alcoholic group, probably of tertiary character.

Reduction of andrographolide with stannous chloride gives a dihydro derivative, m. p. 200° , whereas catalytic hydrogenation in presence of palladium gives an isomeric compound, m. p. 206° . A mixture of the two compounds melts at $183-85^{\circ}$, and hence they are different from each other. Bromination gives an additive compound, contaminated with higher bromination products. Andrographolide absorbs one molecule of hydrogen chloride, forming a compound, $C_{20}H_{31}O_5Cl$, m. p. $55-57^{\circ}$, but the additive compound with hydrogen bromide could not be obtained pure. Iodine chloride indicates the presence of one double bond. Andrographolide is consequently an unsaturated compound.

According to Gorter, andrographolide reacts with anhydrous formic acid forming a compound, m. p. 215° ; we find, however, that our compound remains unchanged by short treatment with this reagent.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Isolation of Andrographolide.—The leaves collected from fully mature plants were dried in the sun, powdered and then extracted with chloroform in a Soxhlet. In the course of two days much green crystalline material was found to float in the solvent, which had assumed a dark greenish brown colour. The green substance was filtered off and further amounts were obtained on concentration of the mother-liquor and cooling. No attempt was made to exhaust the leaves of the bitter principle as this invariably led to difficulty in purification. The crude green mass was washed with benzene, and re-extracted with chloroform in a smaller Soxhlet to remove much of the leaf-pigments. The crystals obtained from the chloroform extract were washed with benzene and repeatedly crystallised from methyl and ethyl alcohol (charcoal) till completely free from colouring matters. Andrographolide was finally obtained as perfectly colourless rectangular plates, or almost cubical crystals, m. p. 220° (decomp.). The yield varied unaccountably from lot to lot, depending possibly on the maturity of the plants. The best yield (2.5%) was obtained from mature plants grown in one of the authors' garden at Dacca, while the samples purchased locally gave as low as 0.8–1% andrographolide.

Andrographolide is sparingly soluble in water, petroleum ether, carbon disulphide, benzene and ether, but dissolves easily in hot chloroform, ethyl

and methyl alcohols, pyridine, ethyl acetate, acetic acid and phenol. (Found: C, 68.0; H, 8.41. $C_{20}H_{30}O_5$ requires C, 68.57; H, 8.57 per cent). A 2% solution in glacial acetic acid in 1 dm. tube showed a rotation of -2.47° . Hence $[\alpha]_D^{30} = -123.5^\circ$.

0.4208 G. of the substance was heated on the water-bath for 2 hours with 7 c.c. of baryta (1 c.c. $\equiv 4.175$ c.c. $N/10-H_2SO_4$) and the excess of alkali was titrated against $N/10-H_2SO_4$. The alkali used up was 3 c.c. Therefore, M.W., is 336, on the basis of a monobasic acid.

isoAndrographolic Acid.—Andrographolide (3.5 g.) was heated on the water-bath for 1 hour with 30 c.c. (7 g. KOH) of aqueous-alcoholic alkali when a clear pale yellow solution resulted. This was shaken for 5 minutes with animal charcoal, filtered, the filtrate cooled in ice and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid till just acidic to Congo-red. The separated colourless needles were collected, washed with water and recrystallised from hot water. m.p. 156° . It liberates carbon dioxide vigorously from a bicarbonate solution. (Found: C, 64.99, 65.03; H, 8.81, 8.21. $C_{20}H_{32}O_6$ requires C, 65.2; H, 8.7 per cent). It gives insoluble barium, calcium, silver and lead salts. The crystalline barium salt was analysed [Found: Ba, 15.00. $(C_{20}H_{31}O_6)_2Ba$ requires Ba, 15.7 per cent].

The same acid was obtained when andrographolide (1 g.) was heated with 2.5 c.c. of baryta solution (2%), the lactone passing in solution within 15 minutes and then the barium salt crystallising out. When the filtered solution was cooled and neutralised with hydrochloric acid, *isoandrographolic acid* was precipitated. If, however, the entire product containing the barium salt be acidified with hydrochloric acid and warmed, the crystals of the barium salt dissolves and on cooling andrographolide is obtained, m.p. after purification, 220° , either alone or admixed with andrographolide.

Andrographolic Acid.—When *isoandrographolic acid* was warmed for 10 minutes with a slight excess of ammonia, cooled and acidified with hydrochloric acid, a little gummy matter was first thrown down. After its removal, the solution gradually deposited silky crystals of another acid, m.p. 180° .

Additive Compounds with Bromine and Halogen Acids.—(a) To andrographolide (3 g.), dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid (d 1.16, 30 c.c.), bromine (1 c.c.) was slowly added. There was rapid decolourisation with evolution of heat. After standing for 1 hour, the mixture was poured into ice. A yellow flocculent solid separated, which was washed with water, dried and purified by dissolving in methyl alcohol and pouring into much water. The pale yellow powder thus obtained melted indefinitely at $128^\circ-140^\circ$. (Found: Br, 38.28. $C_{20}H_{30}Br_2$ requires Br, 31.37 per cent).

(b) To 2 g. of andrographolide dissolved in acetic acid (30 c.c.) was added 1 c.c. of bromine in 10 c.c. of acetic acid. One such sample was kept in bright sunlight for 2 hours and the other was kept overnight. The contents of each were poured into a strong solution of ammonium acetate, when a flocculent precipitate was obtained. This was purified as described above. Identical products were obtained in the two cases, m.p. 110-12° (decomp.). (Found: Br, 34.36, 34.24. $C_{20}H_{30}O_5Br_2$ requires Br, 31.37 per cent).

(c) Andrographolide (2 g.) was shaken with 10 c.c. of saturated hydrogen bromide solution for 18 hours and the product was poured into concentrated ammonium acetate solution. The precipitate was collected, washed thoroughly with water and then boiled with charcoal in methyl alcohol for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The filtered solution was cooled and poured into water. This process was repeated, when a hydrobromide was obtained as a nearly white powder, melting indefinitely between 117° and 124°. (Found: Br, 23.3. $C_{20}H_{31}O_5Br$ requires Br, 18.5 per cent)

(d) Andrographolide (2 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid and the solution was saturated with hydrochloric acid gas. The solution was kept sealed in a tube overnight at the ordinary temperature and then poured into water containing ammonium acetate. The precipitate was collected, dissolved in rectified spirit, boiled with charcoal and filtered. The filtrate was cooled and poured into water. The precipitate was collected and dried in *vacuo* over calcium chloride and sodium hydroxide. A white crystalline powder, m. p. 56-57°, was obtained. (Found: Cl, 9.15. $C_{20}H_{31}O_5Cl$ requires Cl, 9.18 per cent).

(e) Andrographolide (0.4082 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid by warming, cooled and to the solution was added Wijs solution [(25 c.c.) containing 0.8468 g. of iodine and 0.8069 g of ICl_3]. The mixture after standing for 24 hours was titrated against 0.0996 N/1-thiosulphate after the addition of 20 c.c. of 10% potassium iodide and 100 c.c. of water. ICl equivalent to 23.55 c.c. of thiosulphate was used up. (Found: Iodine Value, 72.9. Calc. for one-double bond, 72.57).

Reduction of Andrographolide: Formation of two Isomeric Dihydro Derivatives.—To finely divided palladium prepared by shaking a concentrated aqueous solution of palladium chloride (1 g.), diluted with 25 c.c. of methyl alcohol, by hydrogen for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, was added andrographolide (0.3026 g.) which rapidly dissolved in the medium and the mixture shaken for 2 hours in hydrogen atmosphere till the absorption of gas (21.1 c.c. at N.T.P.) was complete (one double bond requires 19.36 c.c.). The solution after removal of palladium was concentrated and then poured into much water, when

crystals of the dihydro derivative were obtained. After recrystallisation it had m.p. 205° (decomp.). (Found : C, 68.87 ; H, 9.69. $C_{20}H_{32}O_5$ requires C, 68.18 ; H, 9.18 per cent).

To a solution of andrographolide (2 g.) in concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) an excess of crystallised stannous chloride was added and the mixture kept overnight and then poured into ice. The precipitated material crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 200° (decomp.). (Found : C, 68.2 ; H, 10.27. $C_{20}H_{32}O_5$ requires C, 68.18 ; H, 9.18 per cent). A mixture of the two reduction products melted at $183-85^{\circ}$.

Tests for the Hydroxyl Group.—(a) Andrographolide was heated with an excess of acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate for 1 hour and then poured into water. The white powder after purification gave C, 70.55%, H, 7.93%. A monoacetylandrographolide requires C, 67.2 ; H, 8.1 per cent. A dehydration product requires C, 72.3 ; H, 8.4 per cent. The analytical data agree with the formula $C_{40}H_{58}O_9$, which may be formed by loss of one molecule of water from two molecule of the substance. The nature of the product is not known.

(b) Andrographolide (1 g.) on being shaken with phosphorus oxychloride (10 c.c.) gradually went into solution (more rapidly on warming). The dark greenish solution after standing for 12 hours was poured into excess of ice-water, when a nearly white flocculent mass separated. It was collected, washed repeatedly with water and dried in vacuum desiccator. It is easily soluble in benzene and alcohol and had m.p. $85^{\circ}-90^{\circ}$ (decomp.). The presence of phosphorus and chlorine was qualitatively demonstrated.

(c) Andrographolide (1 g.), dissolved in acetic anhydride (5 c.c.), was heated at 100° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour with phenyl isocyanate (3 g.) with constant shaking. There was a vigorous reaction with evolution of gas but no solid separated out. Dilution of the cooled product with dry petroleum ether precipitated a white gummy solid. This was collected, washed with dry petroleum ether, dissolved in dry benzene and reprecipitated with petroleum ether. This process was repeated 5 times, when a white amorphous powder, melting indefinitely at $90-95^{\circ}$, was obtained after drying in vacuum desiccator. It is easily soluble in most organic solvents excepting petroleum ether and water.

Further work is in progress.

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